

Trace and rare earth elements in the new gabbro-norite geochemical reference material

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Abstract : Geochemical analysis of rock and related materials involves determination of major oxides, minor and trace elements, out of which precise determination of trace elements including rare earth elements (REE) is difficult as it involves stringent sample processing and analysis protocols. Trace elements which includes large ion lithophile elements (LILE), high field strength elements (HFSE) and REE, are used in several geochemical discrimination plots to decipher tectonic settings, crystallization history, mineral paragenesis, etc., and hence their accurate determination is important in order to derive meaningful conclusions. Several methods prescribing digestion procedures are available in literature, which are meant for analysis of specific group of elements. An attempt is made here in this study to compare the different digestion techniques viz. open acid digestion, closed acid digestion and fusion methods for effective recovery of trace and REE. Two new geochemical reference materials under preparation at the CSIR-NGRI viz. high and low grade PGE ores, collected from gabbro-norite body in Baula-Nuasahi Complex, Odisha were used not only to evaluate the effectiveness of acid dissolution for many trace elements including REE, but also to determine informative values of analytes measured. The data acquired from inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) were subjected to removal of outliers (analyte outlying from the assigned value) using measures of central tendency and Z-scores. The trace elements values were then compiled for individual digestion methods for low and high grade samples, which were found to be nearer to the assigned value (within 5 to 6% RSD for most the analytes). Out of all the digestion techniques, the closed digestion method was found to be more effective in recovering most of the trace elements.

Keywords : Trace elements, reference material, digestion techniques, ICP-MS, high and low grade PGE ores.

Introduction

Over the past four decades, inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) has been proven to be the most powerful technique for the determination of trace and ultra-trace elements in variety of geological materials, wherein their digestion/decomposition is an important factor in precise data acquisition¹⁻⁴. Sample digestion is wet process of matrix dissolution, in which components of solid sample is converted into solution form. The extent of decomposition of the original sample components is mainly dictated by the analytical methods used. If the goal of the analysis is the determination of the total contents of elements present in the matrices in trace amounts, complete dissolution should be achieved. Chemical composition, degree of crystallinity of the mineral phases, and complexity of the geological material make it necessary to choose a sample decomposition technique

commensurate with the specific objective of the analysis. As a result, there is no single decomposition technique capable of dissolving all elements in all types of geological samples. Nevertheless, a satisfactory or feasible decomposition technique can be devised for the dissolution of a given type of sample for the determination of selected elements.

The most abundant rock types in earth's crust and upper mantle contain silicates, carbonates and oxides as the major components in their matrix for which acid digestion methods are sufficient. HF is a very important dissolving reagent, together with HCl, HNO₃ and HClO₄. Here, besides the effect of the acid, the complexing abilities of the anion of the acids used (fluorides, chlorides) towards the components of inorganic matrix are of importance. But, these sample dissolution methods cannot dissolve highly resistive and refractive minerals. In pre-

vious studies it has been found that alkali fusion is an useful alternative technique capable of decomposition of refractory minerals. Fusion digestion technique has many advantages over the conventional open- and closed-acid digestion methods. It does not require dangerous HF, dissolves all common rock-forming minerals, including zircon and chromite and moreover it is very fast process and many samples can be handled at a time. The combined LiBO_2 fusion and HNO_3 acid digestion is an effective decomposition technique for trace elements⁵. Sample solution prepared from all of these methods were analysed in ICP-MS and results were compared. Outliers were removed using various methods and results were analysed to provide suitable techniques for particular elements. An attempt is made here to compare various analytical methods for two geochemical Reference Materials (low and high grade PGE ore) from Baula-Nuasahi Ultramafic Layered Complex and to provide informative values for the analytes.

PGE reference material from Baula-Nuasahi complex :

The Baula-Nuasahi Complex in southern part of Singhbhum Archaean nucleus in Eastern India exposes series of mafic/ultramafic suites from which the Bangur gabbro (~3.1 Ga) body in the southern part of the complex is significant for platinum group elements (PGE) mineralization. Two types of PGE mineralization have been identified and reference material was prepared representing each type.

- Type 1 representing low grade PGE ore, is a contact type “magmatic” mineralization which occurs between Bangur intrusion and its ultramafic host.
- Type 2 representing high grade PGE ore is restricted within the breccias matrix (within the gabbro body) associated with intense “hydrothermal” alteration⁶.

Materials and methods :

Teflon (PTFE) vessels were used for open digestion method. Savillex[®] pressure decomposition vessels obtained from the M/s Savillex Corporation Minnetonka, MN, USA were used for closed digestion method. Carbon crucibles (10 ml) obtained from Ultra Carbon Division, Carbone of America, USA, were used for fusion method. Electronic grade HF, analytical reagent (AR) grade HClO_4 , distilled HNO_3 and HCl and lithium metaborate (AR grade) were used during the sample preparation. Millipore puri-

fied water (18 Ω) was used in all investigations. JGb-1 and JGb-2 geochemical reference materials for gabbro procured from Geological Society of Japan were used for calibration and checking accuracy/precision of the analysis.

Sample preparation :

Open-acid digestion method :

In open digestion method 10 ml of acid mixture (HF : HNO_3 : HClO_4 :: 7 : 3 : 1) was added to 0.05 g of sample powder in Teflon (PTFE) beaker and left for overnight digestion. The following day sample solutions were heated on hotplate with lids at ~170 °C for 20 min. Then lids were removed to form dry crystalline paste. 5 ml of acid mixture was again added and dried. 20 ml of 1 : 1 HNO_3 was added and warmed (~90 °C) with lids to dissolve the precipitate. 5 ml of 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ^{103}Rh was added as internal standard and volume made up to 250 ml with double distilled water and stored in 60 ml HDPE bottles.

Closed-acid digestion method :

In this method 0.05 g of sample was taken in Savillex[®] Teflon pressure decomposition vessels and 10 ml of acid mixture (HF : HNO_3 : HCl :: 7 : 3 : 2) was added to each vessel. Tightly closed vessels were kept on hotplate for 72 h at ~140 °C. Following this, vessels were opened and contents were evaporated to near dryness. 10 ml of 1 : 1 HNO_3 was added to each vessel and kept on hotplate at ~90 °C for 10 min to dissolve residue. Subsequently 5 ml of 1 ppm ^{103}Rh was added as internal standard and volume was made up to 250 ml with double distilled water and stored in 60 ml HDPE bottles.

Lithium metaborate fusion method :

In fusion method 0.05 g of sample and 0.25 g of lithium metaborate were weighed together, mixed thoroughly in carbon crucible and fused at 1050 °C for 30 min in muffle furnace. The crucible was cooled to room temperature and bead is transferred to a beaker containing 25 ml of 5% HNO_3 and 5 ml of 1 ppm ^{103}Rh as internal standard. The solution was continuously stirred using magnetic stirrer for about 20 min for complete dissolution of the bead. The solution was filtered to remove suspended carbon particles and volume made up to 250 ml with double distilled water and stored in 60 ml HDPE bottles.

The details of the geochemical reference materials used in this study are as follows :

Low grade PGE ore – Bangur gabbro representing type 1 PGE mineralization :

PGE mineralisation exposed in the southern part of the Baula-Nuasahi Complex, the Bangur gabbro forms an oblong intrusion of gabbro-norite cutting the gabbro-anorthosite, peridotite and pyroxenite units. The gabbro displays large (up to 1 cm) euhedral crystals of cumulus plagioclase, orthopyroxene, and clinopyroxene; locally, pyroxene poikilitically encloses plagioclase. Hydrothermal alteration is generally weak, and magmatic textures are preserved.

High grade PGE ore – Bangur gabbro breccia apophysis representing type 2 PGE mineralisation :

A N-NW trending curvilinear apophysis of the Bangur intrusion cuts obliquely across the gabbro-anorthosite and peridotite units. It continues for a strike length of 2 km, and defines a 1 to 40 m wide zone of magmatic breccia with country rock xenoliths in a gabbro matrix. The matrix gabbro hosts the Type 2 PGE and BMS mineralisation and, in contrast to the Bangur gabbro, and shows significant hydrothermal alteration with the development of secondary hydrous minerals⁶.

Instrumentation :

An ICP-MS Perkin-Elmer Sciex (Model ELAN DRC II Toronto, Canada) was used for trace elements analysis. The sample introduction system consisted of a standard Meinhard nebulizer with a cyclonic spray chamber attached to an autosampler (CETAC ASX-500). All quantitative measurements were performed using instrument software. The instrumental parameters and operating conditions of the ICP-MS (Table 1) were set using a procedure described by Balaram and Rao (2003)⁷, such that a

uniform sensitivity was obtained for all the masses across the entire mass range.

Data analysis :

Data were obtained for all the samples including standards, for all these three digestion methods. JGb-2 was analysed as an unknown to get the accuracy. Outliers were removed after plotting each of the analytes for each sample and those values which lie beyond 10% of the central value were rejected. The mean (assigned value), standard deviation and range for each element were calculated. Further, using these values Z-scores were determined. Results showing Z-score beyond the range of ±2 were rejected as outliers.

Z-Scores :

The Z-score is a parameter to evaluate laboratories performance and also to reject outliers. The Z-scores, Z_i are calculated from the laboratory results, the assigned value and the standard deviation using following equation :

$$Z_i = \frac{x - X}{s}$$

where x , X and s are the laboratory result, assigned consensus value and standard deviation respectively. The assigned value is calculated from the average of all laboratory results. The result obtained is rejected as an outlier if numeric value of $Z > 2$.

Results and discussion

Identifying outliers :

The Tables (2 to 7) show the trace element data, their mean values, standard deviation RSD and Z-scores for each of three digestion procedures separately for both types of samples viz. low PGE and high PGE grade. The values blocked in dark/bold colour are the outliers removed by visual and graphical methods (by simple plotting and using measures of central tendency), while light coloured values are those removed after determination of Z-scores. For open acid digestion technique in low PGE samples, there were no outliers detected and in high PGE samples a single outlier was detected (H-1). Outliers detected for closed acid digestion (11 elements in low PGE samples and 10 elements in high PGE samples) are much lesser than that for lithium metaborate fusion method (52

Table 1. Instrumental parameters of ICP-MS

RF Power	1100 W
Argon gas-flow :	
Nebulizer	0.90 L/min
Auxiliary	1.20 L/min
Plasma	15.00 L/min
Lens voltage	7.5 V
Data acquisition mode	Peak hopping
Dwell time	50 ms
Sweeps per reading	40
Replicates	3

Table 2. Analytical data (in µg/g) of low grade PGE reference material by open acid digestion method after removing the outliers

Analytes	Mass No.	Concentration in µg/g					Mean/assigned value	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	RSD	Z-score				
		L-5	L-4	L-3	L-2	L-1						L-5	L-4	L-3	L-2	L-1
Sc	45	28.44	30.61	29.40	28.63	29.27	0.984	28.44	30.61	3.363	-0.85	1.36	0.13	-0.65		
V	51	210.4	226.4	219.6	212.7	217.3	7.246	210.4	226.4	3.335	-0.95	1.26	0.32	-0.63		
Cr	52	628.0	656.3	578.4	595.9	614.6	34.51	578.4	656.3	5.614	0.39	1.21	-1.05	-0.54		
Co	59	44.26	48.29	45.91	43.69	45.54	2.064	43.69	48.29	4.534	-0.62	1.33	0.18	-0.90		
Ni	60	151.1	173.6	155.8	143.2	155.9	12.88	143.2	173.6	8.260	-0.38	1.37	-0.01	-0.99		
Cu	63	137.4	149.2	142.4	141.5	142.6	4.888	137.4	149.2	3.427	-1.06	1.35	-0.05	-0.23		
Zn	66	102.6	108.0	87.80	77.11	93.89	14.08	77.11	108.0	15.00	0.62	1.00	-0.43	-1.19		
Ga	71	19.02	18.20	19.04	19.17	18.85	0.444	18.20	19.17	2.355	0.37	-1.48	0.41	0.70		
Rb	85	16.86	16.15	16.50	16.77	16.57	0.320	16.15	16.86	1.929	0.91	-1.32	-0.22	0.62		
Sr	88	317.7	301.6	318.0	323.3	315.2	9.394	301.6	323.3	2.981	0.27	-1.44	0.30	0.87		
Y	89	12.55	13.36	12.96	12.62	12.87	0.373	12.55	13.36	2.899	-0.87	1.31	0.24	-0.68		
Zr	90	23.65	25.96	19.37	18.21	21.80	3.629	18.21	25.96	16.65	0.51	1.15	-0.67	-0.99		
Nb	93	2.142	2.338	2.253	2.176	2.23	0.087	2.142	2.338	3.916	-0.98	1.27	0.30	-0.59		
Cs	133	0.663	0.697	0.651	0.639	0.66	0.025	0.639	0.697	3.774	0.02	1.38	-0.46	-0.94		
Ba	138	239.7	232.6	240.7	239.6	238.2	3.748	232.6	240.7	1.574	0.42	-1.49	0.68	0.39		
La	139	8.353	8.377	8.585	8.33	8.41	0.117	8.33	8.585	1.396	-0.50	-0.29	1.48	-0.69		
Ce	140	13.79	14.13	14.12	13.84	13.97	0.179	13.79	14.13	1.282	-1.00	0.90	0.82	-0.72		
Pr	141	1.676	1.73	1.736	1.707	1.71	0.027	1.676	1.736	1.589	-1.33	0.65	0.87	-0.19		
Nd	146	7.071	7.391	7.177	7.013	7.16	0.166	7.013	7.391	2.324	-0.55	1.37	0.08	-0.90		
Sm	147	1.642	1.729	1.728	1.632	1.68	0.053	1.632	1.729	3.149	-0.77	0.87	0.85	-0.96		
Eu	151	1.037	1.024	1.061	1.075	1.05	0.023	1.024	1.075	2.193	-0.53	-1.10	0.51	1.12		
Gd	157	1.92	2.042	2.005	1.976	1.99	0.051	1.92	2.042	2.593	-1.28	1.09	0.37	-0.19		
Tb	159	0.337	0.352	0.35	0.337	0.34	0.008	0.337	0.352	2.362	-0.86	0.98	0.74	-0.86		
Dy	163	1.713	1.843	1.775	1.767	1.77	0.053	1.713	1.843	3.005	-1.15	1.28	0.01	-0.14		
Ho	165	0.367	0.396	0.386	0.369	0.38	0.014	0.367	0.396	3.667	-0.90	1.19	0.47	-0.75		
Er	166	1.268	1.325	1.31	1.242	1.29	0.038	1.242	1.325	2.963	-0.48	1.02	0.62	-1.16		
Tm	169	0.186	0.196	0.191	0.189	0.19	0.004	0.186	0.196	2.206	-1.07	1.31	0.12	-0.36		
Yb	172	1.156	1.277	1.211	1.184	1.21	0.052	1.156	1.277	4.291	-0.98	1.35	0.08	-0.44		
Lu	175	0.19	0.208	0.198	0.185	0.20	0.010	0.185	0.208	5.145	-0.52	1.27	0.27	-1.02		
Hf	178	0.66	0.791	0.593	0.606	0.66	0.090	0.593	0.791	13.65	-0.03	1.42	-0.77	-0.62		
Ta	181	0.154	0.17	0.161	0.165	0.16	0.007	0.154	0.17	4.159	-1.26	1.11	-0.22	0.37		
Pb	208	1.606	1.622	1.613	1.554	1.60	0.031	1.554	1.622	1.910	0.24	0.76	0.47	-1.47		
Th	232	1.437	1.772	1.489	1.625	1.58	0.150	1.437	1.772	9.497	-0.96	1.27	-0.61	0.29		
U	238	0.46	0.58	0.47	0.598	0.53	0.072	0.46	0.598	13.68	-0.93	0.74	-0.79	0.98		

Table 3. Analytical data (in µg/g) of high grade PGE reference material by open acid digestion method after removing the outliers

Analytes	Mass no.	Concentration in µg/g					Mean/assigned value	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	RSD	Z-score				
		H-1	H-2	H-3	H-4	H-5						H-1	H-2	H-3	H-4	H-5
Sc	45	30.28	31.09	31.37	31.33	31.78	31.17	0.556	30.28	31.78	1.784	-1.60	-0.14	0.35	0.28	1.10
Y	51	582.6	544.8	563.1	771.1	770.4	646.4	114.3	544.8	771.1	17.68	-0.56	-0.89	-0.73	1.09	1.08
Cr	52	23686	20182	21805	39383	38513	28714	9429	20182	39383	32.84	-0.53	-0.90	-0.73	1.13	1.04
Co	59	82.46	77.88	81.62	106.9	105.3	90.84	14.06	77.88	106.9	15.48	-0.60	-0.92	-0.66	1.14	1.03
Ni	60	269.9	219.6	225.1	238.3	240.7	238.7	19.53	219.6	269.9	8.181	1.60	-0.98	-0.69	-0.02	0.10
Cu	63	163.7	174.0	158.6	162.0	171.9	166.1	6.607	158.6	174.0	3.979	-0.35	1.21	-1.12	-0.61	0.88
Zn	66	181.8	177.6	192.7	239.8	226.7	203.7	27.90	177.6	239.8	13.70	-0.79	-0.94	-0.39	1.29	0.82
Ga	71	16.00	15.19	15.80	19.56	19.55	17.22	2.152	15.19	19.56	12.50	-0.57	-0.94	-0.66	1.09	1.08
Rb	85	5.456	5.542	5.65	5.532	5.507	5.537	0.071	5.46	5.65	1.286	-1.14	0.06	1.58	-0.08	-0.43
Sr	88	107.8	107.1	109.2	107.7	106.7	107.7	0.968	106.7	109.2	0.899	0.10	-0.61	1.57	0.02	-1.08
Y	89	11.31	11.30	11.52	11.50	11.44	11.41	0.105	11.30	11.52	0.917	-0.98	-1.13	1.03	0.79	0.29
Zr	90	28.00	30.46	29.11	31.66	30.30	29.91	1.397	28.00	31.66	4.672	-1.36	0.40	-0.57	1.26	0.28
Nb	93	1.141	1.598	1.710	1.782	1.806	1.607	0.273	1.14	1.81	16.98	-1.71	-0.03	0.38	0.64	0.73
Cs	133	0.693	0.694	0.719	0.675	0.684	0.693	0.016	0.68	0.72	2.373	0.00	0.06	1.58	-1.09	-0.55
Ba	138	107.5	111.5	117.2	109.5	110.4	111.2	3.646	107.5	117.2	3.278	-1.02	0.07	1.64	-0.47	-0.22
La	139	4.948	4.923	4.885	4.922	5.075	4.951	0.073	4.89	5.08	1.476	-0.04	-0.38	-0.90	-0.39	1.70
Ce	140	9.274	9.273	9.048	9.417	9.279	9.258	0.133	9.05	9.42	1.432	0.12	0.11	-1.59	1.20	0.16
Pr	141	1.229	1.213	1.22	1.251	1.230	1.229	0.014	1.21	1.25	1.166	0.03	-1.09	-0.60	1.56	0.10
Nd	146	5.639	5.509	5.68	5.78	5.703	5.662	0.100	5.51	5.78	1.763	-0.23	-1.53	0.18	1.18	0.41
Sm	147	1.454	1.473	1.448	1.499	1.449	1.465	0.022	1.45	1.50	1.482	-0.49	0.39	-0.76	1.58	-0.72
Eu	151	0.568	0.559	0.568	0.578	0.604	0.575	0.017	0.56	0.60	3.014	-0.43	-0.95	-0.43	0.15	1.65
Gd	157	1.728	1.738	1.734	1.75	1.799	1.750	0.029	1.73	1.80	1.638	-0.76	-0.41	-0.55	0.01	1.72
Tb	159	0.322	0.315	0.331	0.325	0.331	0.325	0.007	0.32	0.33	2.070	-0.42	-1.46	0.92	0.03	0.92
Dy	163	1.660	1.663	1.712	1.728	1.713	1.695	0.031	1.66	1.73	1.854	-1.12	-1.02	0.53	1.04	0.57
Ho	165	0.344	0.358	0.353	0.363	0.359	0.355	0.007	0.34	0.36	2.054	-1.56	0.36	-0.33	1.04	0.49
Er	166	1.186	1.176	1.188	1.203	1.247	1.2	0.028	1.18	1.25	2.333	-0.50	-0.86	-0.43	0.11	1.68
Tm	169	0.171	0.171	0.178	0.169	0.181	0.174	0.005	0.17	0.18	2.986	-0.58	-0.58	0.77	-0.96	1.35
Yb	172	1.093	1.14	1.088	1.125	1.124	1.114	0.022	1.09	1.14	2.014	-0.94	1.16	-1.16	0.49	0.45
Lu	175	0.173	0.176	0.172	0.178	0.179	0.176	0.003	0.17	0.18	1.737	-0.85	0.13	-1.18	0.79	1.11
Hf	178	0.783	0.848	0.843	0.959	0.925	0.872	0.070	0.78	0.96	8.055	-1.26	-0.34	-0.41	1.24	0.76
Ta	181	0.055	0.096	0.103	0.117	0.127	0.111	0.014	0.10	0.13	12.56	-4.01	-1.06	-0.56	0.45	1.17
Pb	208	2.488	2.011	2.235	1.936	1.856	2.105	0.256	1.86	2.49	12.18	1.49	-0.37	0.51	-0.66	0.97
Th	232	1.097	1.24	1.055	1.168	1.010	1.114	0.091	1.01	1.24	8.200	-0.19	1.38	0.65	0.59	1.14
U	238	0.390	0.421	0.326	0.383	0.348	0.374	0.037	0.33	0.42	9.948	0.44	1.28	1.28	0.25	0.69

Table 4. Analytical data (in µg/g) of low grade PGE reference material by closed acid digestion method after removing the outliers

Analytes	Mass no.	Concentration in µg/g					Mean/assigned value	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	RSD	Z-score				
		L-1	L-2	L-3	L-4	L-5						L-1	L-2	L-3	L-4	L-5
Sc	45	26.70	26.47	24.70	27.05	27.95	26.57	1.189	24.70	27.95	4.473	0.10	-0.09	-1.57	0.40	1.16
V	51	203.9	204.0	199.1	205.7	206.1	203.8	2.783	199.1	206.1	1.366	0.06	0.08	-1.67	0.70	0.83
Cr	52	257.2	260.4	237.6	248.5	247.5	250.2	8.957	237.6	260.4	3.579	0.78	1.13	-1.41	-0.19	-0.31
Co	59	43.99	44.81	43.43	44.86	43.94	44.21	0.617	43.43	44.86	1.396	-0.36	0.98	-1.26	1.06	-0.42
Ni	60	167.8	185.1	173.7	172.7	167.8	173.4	7.071	167.8	185.1	4.077	-0.80	1.65	0.04	-0.10	-0.79
Cu	63	166.3	168.2	160.4	157.3	167.5	163.9	4.821	157.3	168.2	2.940	0.48	0.89	-0.74	-1.37	0.74
Zn	66	73.07	85.34	65.86	72.57	77.74	72.31	4.887	65.86	77.74	6.759	0.16	2.67	-1.32	0.05	1.11
Ga	71	18.54	18.24	18.24	18.92	18.56	18.50	0.280	18.24	18.92	1.511	0.13	-0.92	-0.92	1.50	0.21
Rb	85	15.13	13.94	13.12	15.03	14.57	14.36	0.836	13.12	15.13	5.821	0.92	-0.50	-1.48	0.81	0.25
Sr	88	296.3	286.3	271.9	303.0	296.8	290.9	12.18	271.9	303.0	4.186	0.45	-0.38	-1.56	1.00	0.49
Y	89	12.35	11.67	10.42	12.40	12.09	12.13	0.335	11.67	12.40	2.765	0.65	-1.37	-5.10	0.82	-0.10
Zr	90	36.14	30.24	21.80	24.18	25.06	23.68	1.687	21.80	25.06	7.124	7.39	3.88	-1.11	0.30	0.82
Nb	93	2.401	2.374	2.380	2.405	2.454	2.403	0.032	2.374	2.454	1.313	-0.06	-0.91	-0.72	0.07	1.62
Cs	133	0.585	0.555	0.483	0.566	0.561	0.55	0.039	0.483	0.585	7.110	0.90	0.13	-1.71	0.41	0.28
Ba	138	144.2	141.8	138.2	145.0	144.4	142.7	2.802	138.2	145.0	1.963	0.51	-0.32	-1.61	0.82	0.60
La	139	8.491	7.781	7.070	8.479	8.232	8.011	0.599	7.07	8.491	7.481	0.80	-0.38	-1.57	0.78	0.37
Ce	140	14.01	13.06	12.09	13.94	13.54	13.33	0.788	12.09	14.01	5.916	0.86	-0.34	-1.57	0.78	0.27
Pr	141	1.618	1.471	1.370	1.602	1.564	1.564	0.066	1.471	1.618	4.211	0.82	-1.41	-2.94	0.58	0.00
Nd	146	6.907	6.481	5.886	7.055	6.673	6.779	0.253	6.481	7.055	3.738	0.51	-1.18	-3.52	1.09	-0.42
Sm	147	1.665	1.525	1.407	1.672	1.589	1.572	0.110	1.407	1.672	6.997	0.85	-0.42	-1.50	0.91	0.16
Eu	151	0.987	0.958	0.906	0.992	0.977	0.964	0.035	0.906	0.992	3.624	0.66	-0.17	-1.66	0.80	0.37
Gd	157	1.854	1.773	1.607	1.910	1.827	1.794	0.116	1.607	1.91	6.449	0.52	-0.18	-1.62	1.00	0.28
Tb	159	0.343	0.315	0.291	0.343	0.329	0.324	0.022	0.291	0.343	6.752	0.86	-0.42	-1.52	0.86	0.22
Dy	163	1.631	1.622	1.434	1.701	1.629	1.603	0.100	1.434	1.701	6.236	0.28	0.19	-1.69	0.98	0.26
Ho	165	0.363	0.341	0.311	0.365	0.356	0.347	0.022	0.311	0.365	6.429	0.71	-0.28	-1.62	0.80	0.39
Er	166	1.265	1.178	1.050	1.243	1.244	1.196	0.088	1.05	1.265	7.350	0.78	-0.20	-1.66	0.53	0.55
Tm	169	0.178	0.168	0.144	0.172	0.174	0.167	0.013	0.144	0.178	8.051	0.80	0.06	-1.72	0.36	0.51
Yb	172	1.149	1.070	0.925	1.145	1.139	1.086	0.095	0.925	1.149	8.791	0.66	-0.16	-1.68	0.62	0.56
Lu	175	0.183	0.175	0.151	0.181	0.180	0.174	0.013	0.151	0.183	7.581	0.68	0.08	-1.74	0.53	0.45
Hf	178	0.908	0.772	0.589	0.621	0.678	0.665	0.080	0.589	0.772	12.07	3.03	1.33	-0.95	-0.55	0.16
Ta	181	0.158	0.173	0.146	0.155	0.157	0.158	0.010	0.146	0.173	6.167	0.02	-1.56	-1.21	-0.29	-0.08
Pb	208	3.958	2.441	3.338	2.335	2.252	2.343	0.095	2.252	2.441	4.044	17.05	1.04	10.51	-0.08	-0.96
Th	232	2.359	1.188	0.979	1.437	1.428	1.258	0.219	0.979	1.437	17.40	5.03	-0.32	-1.27	0.82	0.78
U	238	0.733	0.470	0.459	0.447	0.468	0.461	0.010	0.447	0.47	2.275	25.93	0.86	-0.19	-1.33	0.67

Table 5. Analytical data (in µg/g) of high grade PGE reference material by closed acid digestion method after removing the outliers

Analytes	Mass no.	Concentration in µg/g					Mean/assig- ned value	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	RSD	Z-score				
		H-1	H-2	H-3	H-4	H-5						H-1	H-2	H-3	H-4	H-5
Sc	45	30	30.31	31.14	29.99	30.62	30.41	0.482	29.99	31.14	1.584	-0.85	-0.22	1.51	-0.87	0.44
V	51	893.4	912.8	909.4	815.7	921.9	890.7	43.12	815.7	921.9	4.841	0.06	0.51	0.44	-1.74	0.72
Cr	52	17401	17822	17297	13179	17932	17613	310.8	17297	17932	1.765	-0.68	0.67	-1.02	-14.27	1.03
Co	59	127.0	129.3	128.6	109.4	130.3	128.8	1.369	127.0	130.3	1.063	-1.30	0.39	-0.16	-14.16	1.07
Ni	60	294.7	293.6	295.0	278.5	297.5	291.9	7.587	278.5	297.5	2.599	0.37	0.23	0.41	-1.76	0.74
Cu	63	177.6	188.0	196.1	185.9	191.7	187.8	6.931	177.6	196.1	3.690	-1.48	0.03	1.18	-0.29	0.56
Zn	66	256.6	255.6	253.5	213.6	259.7	247.8	19.27	213.6	259.7	7.776	0.46	0.41	0.29	-1.78	0.62
Ga	71	22.31	22.66	22.39	20.99	22.91	22.25	0.744	20.99	22.91	3.345	0.08	0.55	0.19	-1.70	0.88
Rb	85	5.402	5.455	5.494	5.452	5.489	5.458	0.037	5.402	5.494	0.675	-1.53	-0.09	0.97	-0.17	0.83
Sr	88	102.1	103.5	105.0	104.3	104.7	103.9	1.165	102.1	105.0	1.122	-1.57	-0.37	0.93	0.36	0.64
Y	89	11.09	11.33	11.43	11.3	11.41	11.31	0.137	11.09	11.43	1.213	-1.64	0.13	0.86	-0.08	0.72
Zr	90	46.35	42.03	41.63	33.28	46.27	44.07	2.595	41.63	46.35	5.888	0.88	-0.79	-0.94	-4.16	0.85
Nb	93	2.004	2.023	2.188	1.942	1.922	1.973	0.048	1.922	2.023	2.453	0.65	1.04	4.45	-0.64	-1.05
Cs	133	0.665	0.659	0.711	0.662	0.702	0.680	0.025	0.659	0.711	3.629	-0.60	-0.84	1.26	-0.72	0.90
Ba	138	61.64	62.39	64.35	69.08	66.16	64.72	3.007	61.64	69.08	4.645	-1.03	-0.78	-0.12	1.45	0.48
La	139	5.05	5.707	5.022	5.015	4.813	4.975	0.109	4.813	5.05	2.192	0.69	6.71	0.43	0.37	-1.49
Ce	140	9.363	10.32	9.292	9.191	9.005	9.213	0.155	9.005	9.363	1.687	0.97	7.12	0.51	-0.14	-1.34
Pr	141	1.197	1.263	1.188	1.194	1.157	1.200	0.039	1.157	1.263	3.230	-0.07	1.63	-0.30	-0.15	-1.10
Nd	146	5.507	5.797	5.575	5.49	5.48	5.570	0.132	5.48	5.797	2.375	-0.47	1.72	0.04	-0.60	-0.68
Sm	147	1.386	1.43	1.428	1.451	1.51	1.441	0.045	1.386	1.51	3.137	-1.22	-0.24	-0.29	0.22	1.53
Eu	151	0.522	0.547	0.554	0.546	0.533	0.540	0.013	0.522	0.554	2.365	-1.44	0.52	1.06	0.44	-0.58
Gd	157	1.681	1.674	1.708	1.669	1.704	1.687	0.018	1.669	1.708	1.051	-0.35	-0.74	1.17	-1.03	0.95
Tb	159	0.297	0.312	0.316	0.309	0.315	0.310	0.008	0.297	0.316	2.473	-1.67	0.29	0.81	-0.10	0.68
Dy	163	1.564	1.6	1.617	1.58	1.648	1.602	0.033	1.564	1.648	2.040	-1.16	-0.06	0.47	-0.67	1.41
Ho	165	0.33	0.344	0.355	0.345	0.337	0.342	0.009	0.33	0.355	2.737	-1.30	0.19	1.37	0.30	-0.56
Er	166	1.168	1.198	1.182	1.215	1.223	1.197	0.023	1.168	1.223	1.899	-1.28	0.04	-0.67	0.78	1.14
Tm	169	0.163	0.166	0.167	0.166	0.165	0.165	0.002	0.163	0.167	0.917	-1.58	0.40	1.06	0.40	-0.26
Yb	172	1.016	1.07	1.049	1.047	1.045	1.045	0.019	1.016	1.07	1.843	-1.53	1.28	0.19	0.08	-0.02
Lu	175	0.16	0.165	0.176	0.165	0.174	0.168	0.007	0.16	0.176	4.015	-1.19	-0.44	1.19	-0.44	0.89
Hf	178	1.149	1.139	1.127	0.924	1.166	1.101	0.100	0.924	1.166	9.080	0.48	0.38	0.26	-1.77	0.65
Ta	181	0.138	0.137	0.313	0.126	0.132	0.133	0.006	0.126	0.138	4.128	0.86	0.68	32.68	-1.32	-0.23
Pb	208	25.98	21.05	5.308	2.965	3.89	4.054	1.180	2.965	5.308	29.11	18.58	14.40	1.06	-0.92	-0.14
Th	232	1.177	1.069	0.944	1.59	0.958	1.037	0.109	0.944	1.177	10.49	1.29	0.29	-0.85	5.08	-0.73
U	238	0.374	0.371	0.331	0.401	0.306	0.357	0.038	0.306	0.401	10.58	0.46	0.38	-0.68	1.18	-1.34

Table 6. Analytical data (in µg/g) of low grade PGE reference material by fusion digestion method after removing the outliers

Analytes	Mass no.	Concentration in µg/g								Mean/assigned value			Z-score							
		L-1	L-2	L-5	L-6	L-7	L-8	Standard deviation	Max	Min	RSD	L-1	L-2	L-5	L-6	L-7	L-8			
Sc	45	34.52	33.63	30.86	30.83	30.26	29.66	31.49	1.727	29.66	34.52	5.484	1.56	1.07	-0.50	-0.51	-0.83	-1.17		
V	51	225.8	225.6	221.2	250.2	216.2	223.4	228.0	13.43	216.2	250.2	5.889	-0.17	-0.18	-0.51	1.65	-0.88	-0.35		
Cr	52	642.9	615.8	604.6	755.3	586.8	749.8	604.1	27.73	586.8	642.9	4.590	1.40	0.42	0.02	5.45	-0.63	5.25		
Co	59	45.43	46.10	45.38	45.76	45.09	47.70	45.84	0.879	45.09	47.70	1.918	-0.57	-0.14	-0.60	-0.36	-0.79	0.89		
Ni	60	123.7	123.3	125.5	124.5	123.4	135.4	128.0	5.552	123.3	135.4	4.337	-0.78	-0.85	-0.46	-0.63	-0.83	1.33		
Cu	63	167.0	162.1	178.2	185.6	206.1	176.3	173.8	9.304	162.1	185.6	5.353	-0.73	-1.26	0.47	1.26	3.46	0.26		
Zn	66	76.09	81.63	71.42	73.30	89.78	72.02	78.16	6.835	71.42	89.78	8.746	-0.30	0.51	-0.99	-0.71	1.70	-0.90		
Ga	71	19.47	19.67	18.95	19.58	19.35	19.17	19.27	0.285	18.95	19.67	1.479	0.70	1.39	-1.14	1.07	0.28	-0.37		
Rb	85	11.4	11.22	11.25	11.66	11.31	11.51	11.47	0.306	11.22	11.66	2.668	-0.42	-0.80	-0.75	0.13	-0.61	-0.18		
Sr	88	301.9	296.5	291.4	301.5	294.3	289.3	294.4	5.773	289.3	301.9	1.961	1.29	0.37	-0.52	1.22	-0.02	-0.89		
Y	89	12.38	12.21	12.31	12.30	12.09	12.57	12.52	0.425	12.09	12.57	3.391	-0.34	-0.74	-0.51	-0.54	-1.03	0.11		
Zr	90	45.23	42.66	42.7	63.45	46.11	156.6	43.11	3.651	42.66	46.11	8.468	0.58	-0.12	-0.11	5.57	0.82	31.09		
Nb	93	2.686	3.362	3.18	3.544	3.184	3.126	3.264	0.159	3.126	3.544	4.876	-2.04	0.75	-0.01	1.50	0.01	-0.23		
Cs	133	0.286	0.272	0.28	0.299	0.282	0.271	0.278	0.012	0.271	0.299	4.342	0.73	-0.51	0.20	1.88	0.37	-0.60		
Ba	138	157.9	158.1	153.5	177.3	153.1	155.9	160.7	8.357	153.1	177.3	5.200	-0.33	-0.31	-0.87	1.99	-0.91	-0.58		
La	139	7.376	7.577	7.258	9.545	6.967	7.343	7.926	1.078	6.967	9.545	13.61	-0.51	-0.32	-0.62	1.50	-0.89	-0.54		
Ce	140	12.09	12.40	11.92	14.24	11.45	11.87	12.70	1.325	11.45	14.24	10.44	-0.46	-0.22	-0.58	1.16	-0.94	-0.63		
Pr	141	1.464	1.459	1.399	1.649	1.36	1.417	1.495	0.134	1.36	1.649	8.989	-0.23	-0.27	-0.71	1.15	-1.00	-0.58		
Nd	146	6.373	6.516	6.422	7.08	6.087	6.301	6.597	0.468	6.087	7.08	7.09	-0.53	-0.40	-0.48	0.10	-0.78	-0.59		
Sm	147	1.432	1.557	1.395	1.435	1.337	1.417	1.446	0.080	1.337	1.557	5.502	-0.40	0.44	-0.65	-0.38	-1.04	-0.50		
Eu	151	0.936	0.889	0.844	0.865	0.853	0.824	0.881	0.040	0.824	0.936	4.592	1.37	0.20	-0.91	-0.39	-0.69	-1.40		
Gd	157	1.674	1.684	1.63	1.757	1.57	1.636	1.678	0.076	1.57	1.757	4.554	-0.34	-0.27	-0.62	0.20	-1.01	-0.58		
Tb	159	0.306	0.297	0.283	0.297	0.285	0.295	0.304	0.021	0.283	0.306	6.980	0.08	-0.35	-1.01	-0.35	-0.91	-0.44		
Dy	163	1.494	1.464	1.416	1.429	1.393	1.472	1.486	0.083	1.393	1.494	5.597	0.10	-0.26	-0.84	-0.69	-1.12	-0.17		
Ho	165	0.334	0.328	0.308	0.318	0.313	0.327	0.326	0.013	0.308	0.334	3.858	0.61	0.13	-1.46	-0.67	-1.06	0.05		
Er	166	1.098	1.088	1.005	1.095	1.027	1.05	1.089	0.064	1.005	1.098	5.855	0.14	-0.02	-1.32	0.09	-0.98	-0.62		
Tm	169	0.16	0.144	0.145	0.148	0.138	0.149	0.151	0.009	0.138	0.16	5.895	1.06	-0.75	-0.63	-0.30	-1.42	-0.18		
Yb	172	1.057	1.024	0.995	1.003	0.954	0.996	1.015	0.035	0.954	1.057	3.455	1.19	0.25	-0.58	-0.35	-1.75	-0.55		
Lu	175	0.165	0.157	0.143	0.149	0.139	0.151	0.152	0.009	0.139	0.165	5.942	1.39	0.51	-1.04	-0.37	-1.48	-0.15		
Hf	178	0.953	0.854	0.849	1.141	0.86	0.896	0.863	0.071	0.849	0.953	8.192	1.28	-0.12	-0.19	3.94	-0.04	0.47		
Ta	181	0.141	0.136	0.119	0.125	0.12	0.123	0.126	0.009	0.119	0.141	6.928	1.69	1.11	-0.83	-0.14	-0.71	-0.37		
Pb	208	3.604	2.504	2.343	3.621	3.478	5.546	2.913	0.621	#REF!	#REF!	21.31	0.89	-0.79	-1.04	0.92	0.70	3.87		
Th	232	0.792	0.928	1.084	0.931	0.776	1.07	1.035	0.301	0.776	1.084	29.10	-0.65	-0.47	-0.26	-0.47	-0.67	-0.28		
U	238	0.223	0.198	0.207	0.212	0.206	0.23	0.215	0.012	0.198	0.23	5.63	0.05	-1.03	-0.64	-0.43	-0.69	0.35		

Table 7. Analytical data (in µg/g) of low grade PGE reference material by fusion digestion method after removing the outliers

Analytes	Mass no.	Concentration in µg/g									Mean/assigned value	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	RSD	Z-score				
		H-1	H-2	H-5	H-8	H-9	H-1	H-2	H-5	H-8						H-9				
Sc	45	23.00	23.15	23.72	24.20	22.92	23.40	0.55	22.9	24.20	2.331	-1.13	-0.92	-0.09	0.61	-1.26				
V	51	645.8	630.6	629.1	665.4	605.5	635.3	22.18	605.5	665.4	3.492	-0.04	-0.64	-0.70	0.73	-1.63				
Cr	52	15349	16260	12094	16059	14602	14873	753.1	14602	16260	5.064	-0.58	0.39	-4.05	0.18	-1.37				
Co	59	101.7	94.75	87.77	93.34	88.53	93.21	5.596	87.77	101.7	6.004	1.36	-0.01	-1.40	-0.29	-1.25				
Ni	60	235.7	183.3	158.2	167.4	159.3	167.1	11.569	158.2	183.3	6.925	7.28	1.67	-1.01	-0.02	-0.89				
Cu	63	216.2	211.9	197.6	179.7	204.2	201.9	14.34	179.7	216.2	7.103	1.36	1.07	0.07	-1.17	0.53				
Zn	66	156.2	152.8	147.4	187.0	153.4	152.4	3.67	147.4	156.2	2.408	-0.05	-0.37	-0.87	2.81	-0.31				
Ga	71	19.14	18.72	17.91	18.76	17.88	18.48	0.561	17.88	19.14	3.034	1.17	0.25	-1.48	0.34	-1.56				
Rb	85	5.625	5.396	5.222	5.583	4.876	5.340	0.305	4.876	5.625	5.72	-0.16	-0.56	-0.87	-0.24	-1.47				
Sr	88	108.5	107.3	107.2	138.8	110.4	114.4	13.66	107.2	138.8	11.94	-0.68	-0.74	-0.75	0.97	-0.58				
Y	89	11.12	10.67	11.00	11.87	10.59	11.05	0.509	10.59	11.87	4.605	-0.39	-1.12	-0.58	0.86	-1.26				
Zr	90	94.73	114.3	101.6	287.6	139.3	112.5	19.65	94.73	139.3	17.47	-1.19	-0.06	-0.79	9.93	1.39				
Nb	93	1.503	1.502	1.253	2.266	1.601	1.625	0.38	1.253	2.266	2.266	-0.58	-0.58	-1.33	1.70	-0.29				
Cs	133	0.238	0.255	0.241	0.245	0.26	0.248	0.009	0.238	0.26	3.779	-0.51	0.68	-0.30	-0.02	1.03				
Ba	138	81.91	72.66	77.96	171.6	122.2	77.51	4.64	72.66	81.9	5.99	-0.23	-0.96	-0.54	6.83	2.94				
La	139	5.409	4.516	4.735	6.362	5.266	5.258	0.719	4.516	6.36	13.67	-0.51	-0.89	-0.80	-0.10	-0.57				
Ce	140	8.759	7.614	8.09	10.54	8.417	8.68	1.120	7.614	10.54	12.90	-0.56	-0.92	-0.77	0.01	-0.67				
Pr	141	1.16	1.008	1.042	1.372	1.147	1.146	0.142	1.008	1.372	12.43	-0.01	-1.15	-0.90	1.58	-0.11				
Nd	146	5.222	4.819	4.902	5.979	5.034	5.191	0.466	4.819	5.979	8.976	-0.05	-0.97	-0.78	1.69	-0.48				
Sm	147	1.197	1.139	1.196	1.44	1.138	1.1675	0.033	1.138	-1.197	2.869	0.31	-0.97	0.29	5.69	-1.00				
Eu	151	0.455	0.437	0.463	0.511	0.455	0.464	0.028	0.437	0.511	6.00	-0.62	-0.95	-0.48	0.39	-0.62				
Gd	157	1.438	1.354	1.412	1.576	1.367	1.429	0.089	1.354	1.576	6.203	-0.03	-1.03	-0.34	1.61	-0.88				
Tb	159	0.258	0.255	0.251	0.288	0.251	0.261	0.016	0.251	0.288	5.985	-0.61	-0.73	-0.90	0.63	-0.90				
Dy	163	1.322	1.228	1.317	1.41	1.273	1.310	0.068	1.228	1.41	5.161	-0.29	-1.39	-0.35	0.73	-0.87				
Ho	165	0.285	0.279	0.286	0.321	0.282	0.291	0.017	0.279	0.321	5.923	-0.78	-1.13	-0.72	1.36	-0.96				
Er	166	0.965	0.927	0.965	1.064	0.955	0.975	0.052	0.927	1.064	5.334	-0.63	-1.28	-0.63	1.08	-0.80				
Tm	169	0.129	0.13	0.136	0.143	0.128	0.133	0.006	0.128	0.143	4.730	-1.08	-0.94	-0.12	0.84	-1.22				
Yb	172	0.866	0.887	0.889	0.915	0.835	0.878	0.030	0.835	0.915	3.398	-0.90	-0.41	-0.36	0.25	-1.63				
Lu	175	0.133	0.133	0.131	0.145	0.136	0.136	0.006	0.131	0.145	4.093	-0.79	-0.79	-1.08	0.94	-0.36				
Hf	178	1.494	2.179	2.056	2.748	2.36	2.198	0.153	2.056	2.36	6.956	-3.41	0.08	-0.55	2.97	1.00				
Ta	181	0.099	0.087	0.126	0.118	0.074	0.101	0.021	0.074	0.126	21.29	-0.10	-0.72	1.31	0.89	-1.40				
Pb	208	32.51	11.58	60.62	9.094	2.816	7.828	4.515	2.816	11.58	57.67	6.58	1.30	13.67	0.67	-0.91				
Th	232	0.59	0.913	0.611	1.017	0.762	0.7786	0.186	0.59	1.017	23.93	-1.23	0.10	-1.15	0.53	-0.52				
U	238	0.195	0.199	0.186	0.234	0.196	0.202	0.019	0.186	0.234	9.18	-0.74	-0.55	-1.16	1.08	-0.69				

ng/g in low PGE and 58 ng/g in high PGE samples). For both acid digestion methods outliers detected by visual and graphical methods show same result using *Z*-score too, while in case of lithium metaborate fusion method many outliers lie within 10% of the central value but show *Z*-scores beyond ± 2 .

Comparison of methods :

Identification and removal of outliers from the tabulated data for trace elements provided better way for the comparison of various decomposition techniques. We rejected two samples (H-7 and L-9) digested by fusion technique based on graphical method and *Z*-score. The sample H-7 contains 79.4% of the element as outliers and L-9 contains 88.2% as outliers. Mean values, standard deviations and relative standard deviations were calculated again removing these samples from fusion method data. Variations in results for each element have been calculated in terms of relative standard deviation for all three techniques.

There is no outlier identified in low PGE samples in case of open digestion, for four samples. RSD for all elements is $< 5\%$, except for Cr, Ni, Lu, Th ($5\% < \text{RSD} < 10\%$) and for Zn, Zr, Hf and U ($10\% < \text{RSD} < 20\%$), in low PGE samples, while in high PGE samples, for all five samples, only one outlier (H-1) has been identified for the analyte Ta. All REEs show accurate results having RSD $< 5\%$. RSD for Ni, Hf, Th, U lies in between 5% to 10%, for V, CO, Zn, Ga, Nb, Ta and Pb it lies in between 10% to 20%, only Cr shows a little higher RSD value of 32.84%.

In closed acid digestion technique, 11 outliers were detected in five low PGE samples (2 REEs viz. Pr and Nd for sample L-3 and 9 other elements viz. Zn, Y, Zr, Hf, Pb, Th and U for samples L-1, L-2 and L-3). All REEs have RSD values range from 5% to 10%, only Pr and Nd show $< 5\%$. For all other trace elements it is $< 10\%$ except Hf (12.07%) and Th (17.4%). In high PGE samples, 10 outliers have been identified for samples H-1, H-2, H-3 and H-4 out of total five samples. 2 outliers identified for REEs La and Ce, while remaining 8 for the elements Cr, Co, Zr, Nb, Ta, Pb and Th. All REEs show RSD values $< 5\%$. RSD for all other elements are also $< 5\%$ except Zn, Zr, Hf ($5\% < \text{RSD} < 10\%$), Th and

U show slightly higher values, 10.49% and 10.58% respectively while Pb shows relatively higher value of 29.11%.

For lithium metaborate fusion method, total of 22 outliers have been detected in low PGE samples L-1, L-3, L-4, L-6, L-7 and L-8 out of total eight samples. Six outliers were detected for light and middle REEs for sample L-4, others have been detected for elements Cr, Co, Cu, Zn, Zr, Nb, Hf, Pb, Th and U. Only 4 REEs Eu, Ho, Gd and Yb showed RSD value $< 5\%$, while all other show in range of 5% to 10%, except for Ce (10.44%) and La (13.61%). For all other elements RSD values are $< 10\%$, except for Pb (21.31%) and Th (29.10%). In high PGE samples, apart from H-7 total of 31 outliers have been identified for samples H-1, H-3, H-4, H-5, H-6, H-8 and H-9 out of 8 samples. 9 outliers are for REEs Pr, Nd, Sm and Gd and remaining for Cr, Ni, Zr, Nb, Hf, Ta, Pb, Th and U. For all REEs RSD values lie in between 5–10% excepting Sm and Yb for lower values of 3.82% and 4.705% respectively and La (35.45%), Ce (29.89%), Pr (11.45%) and Eu (11.29%) for higher values. For most of the other elements these values are $< 10\%$, but many elements show much more variations in RSD as Sr (15.18%), Zr (15.05%), Nb (19.73%), Ba (14.99%), Ta (19.04%), Pb (exceptionally high 61.54%) and Th (27.25%).

Comparing RSD values of all the trace elements in open digestion, for low PGE samples only four RSD values are more than 10% (for Cr, Ni, Lu and Th) and for high PGE samples only 8 values are more than 10% (for V, Cr, Co, Zn, Ga, Nb, Ta and Pb). In closed digestion method, for low PGE samples, there are only two RSD values slightly more than 10% (12.07% for Hf and 17.40% for Th) and for high PGE samples, all RSD values are $\leq 10\%$ except a single one, 29.11% for Pb. In fusion method, for low PGE samples four RSD values are more than 10%, Th and Pb show relatively higher RSD value of 29.10% and 21.31% respectively. For high PGE samples, eight RSD values are in the range of 10–30%, whereas Pb shows exception high value of 61.54%. This indicates that the closed digestion technique provides more precise results as compared to open digestion which in turn gives more precise results than fusion method.

Table 8. Compiled informative values (in µg/g) for trace and REE in low and high grade PGE ores

Analytes	Low grade PGE ore				High grade PGE ore			
	Open acid digestion	Close acid digestion	Lithium methaborate fusion	Mean (Informative values)	Open acid digestion	Close acid digestion	Lithium methaborate fusion	Mean (Informative values)
Sc	29.27	26.57	31.49	29.11	31.17	30.41	23.78	28.45
V	217.3	203.8	228.0	216.37	646.4	890.7	646.8	727.94
Cr	614.6	250.2	604.1	489.66	28714	17613	15890	20739.01
Co	45.54	44.21	45.84	45.20	90.84	128.8	94.82	104.82
Ni	155.9	173.4	128.0	152.46	238.7	291.9	167.7	232.75
Cu	142.6	163.9	173.8	160.13	166.1	187.8	196.5	183.47
Zn	93.89	72.31	78.16	81.45	203.7	247.8	156.7	202.74
Ga	18.85	18.50	19.27	18.87	17.22	22.25	18.60	19.36
Rb	16.57	14.36	11.47	14.13	5.537	5.458	5.719	5.57
Sr	315.2	290.9	294.4	300.15	107.7	103.9	120.9	110.85
Y	12.87	12.13	12.52	12.51	11.41	11.31	11.35	11.36
Zr	21.80	23.68	43.11	29.53	29.91	44.07	115.3	63.09
Nb	2.23	2.403	3.264	2.63	1.607	1.973	1.697	1.76
Cs	0.66	0.55	0.278	0.50	0.693	0.680	0.245	0.54
Ba	238.2	142.7	160.7	180.53	111.2	64.72	84.84	86.93
La	8.41	8.011	7.926	8.12	4.951	4.975	6.598	5.51
Ce	13.97	13.33	12.70	13.33	9.258	9.213	10.52	9.66
Pr	1.71	1.564	1.495	1.59	1.229	1.200	1.161	1.20
Nd	7.16	6.779	6.597	6.85	5.662	5.570	5.244	5.49
Sm	1.68	1.572	1.446	1.57	1.465	1.441	1.183	1.36
Eu	1.05	0.964	0.881	0.96	0.575	0.540	0.490	0.54
Gd	1.99	1.794	1.678	1.82	1.750	1.687	1.441	1.63
Tb	0.34	0.324	0.304	0.32	0.325	0.310	0.273	0.30
Dy	1.77	1.603	1.486	1.62	1.695	1.602	1.347	1.55
Ho	0.38	0.347	0.326	0.35	0.355	0.342	0.298	0.33
Er	1.29	1.196	1.089	1.19	1.2	1.197	1.001	1.13
Tm	0.19	0.167	0.151	0.17	0.174	0.165	0.137	0.16
Yb	1.21	1.086	1.015	1.10	1.114	1.045	0.905	1.02
Lu	0.20	0.174	0.152	0.17	0.176	0.168	0.139	0.16
Hf	0.66	0.665	0.863	0.73	0.872	1.101	2.164	1.38
Ta	0.16	0.158	0.126	0.15	0.111	0.133	0.101	0.11
Pb	1.60	2.343	2.913	2.28	2.105	4.054	6.440	4.20
Th	1.58	1.258	1.035	1.29	1.114	1.037	0.889	1.01
U	0.53	0.461	0.215	0.40	0.374	0.357	0.211	0.31

From these observations, it can be inferred that among REEs, only lighter REEs (La and Ce) show RSD values range from 10–15% for fusion method. In closed digestion methods all RSD values are <10% for low PGE samples and even <5% among high PGE samples. For open digestion method, all RSD values are ≤5% for low

PGE samples while it is ≤3% for high PGE samples. This also indicates that lighter REEs show more RSD values as compared to middle and heavy REEs. Open acid digestion technique provided more precise results for REEs than closed acid digestion method, which in turn provided more precision as compared to lithium

metaborate fusion method. However, in closed acid digestion method, high PGE sample results are more precise compared to low PGE samples.

Conclusion

Two geochemical reference materials containing low PGE (less than 0.5 ppm) and high PGE (more than 0.5 ppm) were analyzed for trace and REE by ICP-MS following open acid digestion, closed acid digestion and fusion methods, to compare and evaluate the efficiency of each analytical method in terms of their recovery. Analytical data indicates that the trace elements determined following closed acid digestion method had reasonably good recovery, accuracy and precision (assessed in terms of %RSD) compared to open digestion and fused method. Using geostatistical methods, individual analyte outliers were removed from each subset of analytical data obtained from open, closed and fusion digestion methods. The average values thus obtained from each of these methods form a set of informative values of trace elements for these two geochemical reference materials for future use.

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